

Performance Analysis of Forest Ranger Technical Implementation Unit of Taka Bonerate National Park in Protection and Security of the Area

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to describe and analyze the implementation of the protection and security of the area, the level of performance of the Forest Ranger of the Taka Bonerate National Park, and formulate a strategy to improve the performance of the Taka Bonerate National Park Forest Ranger in implementing the protection and security of the area. This research is descriptive research with a qualitative approach. The results showed that the implementation of the main tasks and functions of the Taka Bonerate National Park Forest Ranger in the protection and security of the area that was most dominantly carried out was Patrol and Guard. The patrols were very effective in preventing regional disturbances, while the guarding activities were less effective because the location and position of the guard post resort cannot monitor fishers' activities directly. After all, the Taka Bonerate National Park area is an open-access waters area. Regional disturbances in Taka Bonerate National Park are divided into two, destructive and illegal fishing, which from 2017 to 2020 fluctuated but tended to decline. The regional disturbance level in the working area of the SPTN Region II of Jinato was higher than the SPTN Region I of Tarupa. The Forest Ranger of Taka Bonerate National Park Office's performance is considered **good**. The average achievement value of employee performance targets in 2020 is above 80, in line with the decrease in regional disturbances. The strategy carried out by the Taka Bonerate National Park Forestry Ranger is to involve the community, involve relevant law enforcement officers, increase the intensity of patrols, and increase the number of personnel. Of the four strategies, the most effective is increasing the intensity of Patrol activities.

Keywords: Forestry Ranger, Performance and Regional Disturbance

I. INTRODUCTION

There are 54 National Parks in Indonesia for now. Seven of them are considered marine areas. The seven marine parks are Thousand Islands National Park in Jakarta, Wakatobi National Park in Southeast Sulawesi, Bunaken National Park in North Sulawesi, Teluk Cendrawasi National Park in West Papua, Karimun Jawa National Park in Semarang, Central Java, Togeang Islands National Park in Central Sulawesi and Taka Bonerate National Park in Fort Selayar South Sulawesi.

The Taka Bonerate National Park (TNTBR) area is a nature conservation area located on the southern side of the Sulawesi Peninsula or in the Flores Sea with 530,765 Ha. The TNTBR area consists of 17 islands,

five *bungins* (sand exposure) and 30 *takas* (coral reef) exposure, scattered to form rings/atolls.

Regional disturbances still occur frequently, although Protection and Security activities have been carried out by prioritizing the Tasks of the Forestry Ranger. The area's problems and disturbances are divided into destructive fishing and illegal fishing. Data on disturbances in the Taka Bonerate National Park area can be seen in Table 1.

Table1.Area Interference Data

No.	Disturbance	Year	Total
1.	<i>Destructive Fishing</i>	2017	23Events
2.	<i>Illegal Fishing</i>	2017	13Events
3.	<i>Destructive Fishing</i>	2018	4Events
4.	<i>Illegal Fishing</i>	2018	22Events
5.	<i>Destructive Fishing</i>	2019	11Events
6.	<i>Illegal Fishing</i>	2019	15Events

Source: Secondary Data (2017-2019)

The data shows regional disturbances in destructive and illegal fishing every year, even though they experience fluctuations. Destructive fishing consists of fish bombing (abuse of explosives), anaesthetizing fish, catching with compressor aids, and taking corals. Meanwhile, Illegal Fishing consists of; uncontrolled fishing such as purse seine (trawl rings), taking protected marine biota and zoning violations.

These disturbances of the area certainly impact on the low performance of the forest Ranger when it is associated with the high level of disturbance in the area and also has an impact on the organization of the Taka Bonerate National Park Office, which accommodates the forest Ranger. The high number of disturbances in the area can lead to negative perceptions of the performance of the forest Ranger, who are the front line in carrying out protection and security activities in the area, even though the impact of high disturbances in the area is not due to the low performance of the forest Ranger, because many factors influence the occurrence of regional disturbances.

The regional disturbances in the Taka Bonerate National Park indicate that the area's protection and security activities are not yet optimal. Prevention efforts by prioritizing Preemptive and Preventive actions carried out by the Forestry Ranger should prevent and suppress area disturbances normatively, but in fact, violations and disturbances to the area in the form of destructive fishing and illegal fishing occur.

According to Government Regulation No. 45 of 2004, forest protection is an effort to prevent and limit damage to forests, forest areas and forest products caused by human actions, livestock, fire, natural resources, pests and diseases, and maintain and protect the rights of the state, community and individuals over forests, forest areas, forest products, investments and instruments related to forest management.

Human resources, including the national park as a conservation area, is the success factor in dealing with regional disturbances. The effectiveness of national park area management lies in the role of personnel in the field. The forestry apparatus on duty spearheads handling regional disturbances in the Forestry Ranger [1].

According to the Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform Number 21 of 2019, Functional Officers of the Forestry Ranger, referred to as Forestry Ranger, are civil servants within the scope of the central and/or regional forestry agencies which under the nature of their work organize and/or carry out forest protection efforts that by the power of law, special Ranger powers are granted in the field of forestry and conservation of living natural resources and their ecosystems.

Performance comes from job performance, the work achievement achieved by someone. It also means work performance, work implementation, work achievement or work results, and performance. Performance

can be seen from two aspects: employees (individuals) and organizational performance. Employee performance is the result of individual work in an organization. At the same time, organizational performance is the totality of the work achieved by an organization.

Every employee in the organization is required to make a positive contribution through good performance, considering that organizational performance depends on the performance of its employees. Performance is the degree to which employees achieve job requirements efficiently and effectively. Employee performance is work performance, which is a comparison between work results that can be seen in real terms with work standards that have been set by the organization [2].

The organization of the TNTBR Center is determined based on the Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number: P.7/Menlhk/Setjen/OTL.O/1/2016 concerning the Organization and Work Procedure of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Taka Bonerate National Park Office by carrying out one of its functions of Protection and Security. In carrying out the technical task of Protection in the field, the Taka Bonerate National Park Hall has human resources (HR) in the Functional Position, namely the Forestry Ranger. So that in the Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number: P.54/Menlhk-Setjen/2015 concerning Standards and Competency Tests for Functional Positions of the Forestry Ranger, the Ranger are carefully prepared before carrying out the task of protecting and securing the area.

Regional disturbances will not be separated from the forest Ranger' performance indicators. The performance of the forest Ranger can be said to be good if the disturbance in the area decreases or there is no disturbance, while the performance of the Ranger is low if the disturbance in the area increases.

II. METHOD

Using a descriptive research method with a qualitative approach, this research seeks to explain descriptively by combining the results of literature studies and data collection results in the field about the implementation of the protection and security of the area by prioritizing the duties of the forest Ranger in preventing disturbances to the TNTBR area. The literature research was carried out by comparing the regulations, provisions, and reference books and the data obtained, then analyzed qualitatively, which will provide a comprehensive picture of the legal aspects related to the problem to be studied [3].

Questionnaires and interview guidelines were how this research data was collected. Interviews with informants were carried out directly, but the researchers also distributed online questionnaires or interview guidelines for unreachable informants. The interviews were conducted to get a measured and in-depth understanding of the data. Furthermore, the results of the interviews were recapitulated and analyzed to conclude each aspect of the study.

Purposive sampling was used to determine the informants. The informants in this study were 1 Head of Administration Sub-Section, the Head of Tarupa Region I Management Section, the Jinato Region II Management Section Head, one TNTBR Forestry Ranger Coordinator, 17 TNTBR Forestry Ranger Officer, 3 Management Partners who are in the TNTBR area, and five people living in the Taka Bonerate National Park area.

The data analysis technique used in this research is the interactive analysis technique developed by Miles & Huberman (1992:15-20) in Suhardi's research which consists of 3 components of analysis, namely data reduction, data presentation (data display) and concluding (verification) [4].

III. RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

The organization of the TNTBR Center is decided based on the Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number: P.7/Menlhk/Setjen/OTL.O/1/2016 concerning the Organization and Work Procedure of the Technical Implementation Unit of the Taka Bonerate National Park Office by carrying out one of its functions

of Protection and Security. In carrying out the technical task of Protection in the field, the Taka Bonerate National Park Hall has human resources (HR) in the Functional Position or known as the Forestry Ranger. Based on the Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform Number 21 of 2019, the positions and responsibilities of the Forestry Ranger are as follows:

1. The Forestry Ranger is located as a technical implementer in Forestry Ranger in government agencies.
2. The Forestry Ranger, as referred to, is located under and directly responsible to the Primary High Management Officer, Administrator Officer, or Supervisory Officer who is related to the implementation of the Forestry Ranger Functional Position.
3. The position of the Forestry Ranger is determined in the position map based on the analysis of the duties and functions of the work unit, job analysis, and workload analysis carried out following the provisions of the legislation.

Currently, protection and security activities at the site level are under the Forestry Ranger hand, but disturbances in the area still occur. And the occurrence of regional disturbances in the area can lead to negative perceptions in the form of low performance of the Forestry Ranger, who are the frontline in preserving the TNTBR area. The lousy performance of the forest Ranger there is not most likely the cause of regional disturbances because many other things affect the occurrence of regional disturbances. On the other hand, if the disturbance of the area decreases from destructive fishing and illegal fishing activities, that means the performance of the forest and forest Ranger is good or increasing, thereby impacting the sustainability of the TNTBR conservation area.

The concepts above are summarized in the framework of thinking as illustrated in Fig.1.

Figure 1. research framework

IV. OPERATIONAL CONCEPT

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Forestry Number: P. 75/Menhut-II/2014 concerning the Forestry Ranger based on Article 4 (1), the duties and functions of the Forestry Ranger are: a. Perform the protection and security of forests, forest areas, forest products of wild flora and fauna; and b. maintain and safeguard the rights of the state, community and individuals to forests, forest products, wild plants and animals, investments and instruments related to forest management

According to Mappatoba and Nuraini in Sudirman Sultan [5], "Prevention is a cheap and effective protection system and is implemented as an effort to prevent one of the many causes of damage from population explosion. Prevention is carried out through long-term programs continuously with careful management.

Preemptive and Preventive Activities in the protection and security of the area should be able to ward off or prevent regional disturbances that occur within the Taka Bonerate National Park area. Preemptive activities in the protection and security of the area are through socialization, counselling, and travelling there or visiting people's homes. Meanwhile, the Preventive activities that the Forestry Ranger often carry out are Patrol and Guard.

According to Simamora [2], "Every employee in the organization is required to make a positive contribution through good performance, considering that organizational performance depends on the performance of its employees. Performance is the degree to which employees achieve job requirements efficiently and effectively. Employee performance is work performance, which compares work results that can be seen in real terms with work standards that the organization has set.

Hadari Nawawi [6] says that performance is (a) something that is achieved, (b) demonstrated achievement, (c) workability. Suppose a work target can be completed at the right time or does not exceed the time limit provided, the performance graded as high standard. Its score becomes low if completed beyond the allotted time limit or not completed at all. The performance appraisal results can indicate whether the human resources have met the demands desired by the hall, both in terms of quality and quantity.

The organization that accommodates the current forest Ranger generally applies to terrestrial or terrestrial areas, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry. However, the forest Ranger work area is on land and in water areas, including the Forestry Ranger of the Taka Bone Rate National Park, where the working place is the sea or water area. This raises the complexity of problems and complicated communication and coordination in carrying out area protection and security activities.

The competence factor of the Forestry Ranger position in carrying out the task of protecting and securing the area is very important because functional positions are categorized in the investigator and detective skill cluster, meaning that a forest Ranger officer must-have skill and proficient abilities.

The initial stage in strategic management is to determine the vision and mission of the organization. Vision and mission are very important because they guide all organizational activities. The organization prepares plans and activities to realize its vision and mission based on the vision and mission. The formulation of the right, clear and appropriate vision and mission are needed before various alternative strategies are formulated and implemented [7]

One of the missions of the Taka Bonerate National Park is to strengthen and improve the protection of marine conservation areas and law enforcement. In order to achieve this mission, the TNTBR Center has formulated and developed a strategy and program for protection and security activities, including involving the surrounding community, involving relevant officials, increasing the intensity of patrol activities, and efforts to increase personnel in the field, especially the Forestry Ranger through the mechanism for proposing the formation of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Taka Bonerate National Park Center is led by a Head of National Park Office (Echelon III. A), assisted by the Head of Sub-Division of Administration (Echelon IV.A) and Section Head of National Park Management I and II (Echelon IV.A) as well as functional groups (KLHK 2016) with the following job descriptions:

1) Head of National Park Office

Organizing the conservation of living natural resources and their ecosystems and managing national park areas based on the applicable laws and regulations.

2) Head of Sub-Division of Administration

Manage the affairs of correspondence, management, staffing, finance, equipment, archives, housekeeping, planning, cooperation, data, monitoring and evaluation, reporting and public relations.

3) Section Head of National Park Management I and II

Formulating plans and budgets, evaluation and reporting, technical guidance, community service and empowerment, area management, protection, preservation, sustainable use, eradication of illegal logging and circulation of wildwood, plants and animals, and management of infrastructure, promotion and development of natural tourism and fostering love for nature, counselling on the conservation of living natural resources and their ecosystems, and cooperation in the management of national park areas.

4) Functional Groups

Carrying out activities under their respective functional positions based on the applicable laws and regulations.

The Taka Bonerate National Park area is divided into 2 (two) management sections, namely the National Park Management Section (SPTN) Region I in Tarupa Village and SPTN Region II in Jinato Village. Each Regional SPTN has staff in charge of general administrative affairs and KSDAE technical affairs.

SPTN Region I oversee five resorts: Resort Tarupa, Resort Rajuni Desa, Resort Tinabo, Resort Rajuni Laut, and Resort Latondu. SPTN Region II oversees Jinato Resort, East Pasitallu Resort, and Central Pasitallu Resort.

Each resort has 2 – 3 functional Forestry Ranger officers and one functional forest ecosystem controller. Meanwhile, there is only one person in each Regional SPTN. There are also TPHL staff, helmspersons and crew members, and honorary staff in each Regional SPTN who are very helpful in carrying out work assignments within the Taka Bonerate National Park area.

VI. Description and Analysis of Protection and Security Aspects

The Forestry Ranger do area protection and security activities as Functional Officials within the Central and Regional Ministry of Environment and Forestry Institutions due to their nature and work to organize and/or carry out forest protection efforts authorized by law to be given special Ranger powers in the area of the forestry and conservation of living natural resources and their ecosystems. However, the Forestry Ranger of the Taka Bonerate National Park oversees the water area, so the special Ranger authority by the forest Ranger is in the field of conservation of natural resources in the waters.

Figure2. some activities done by Forestry Ranger

It is illustrated in Figure 1 that the Forestry Ranger of TNTBR carrying out patrols, guarding, and conducting outreach to the community has the highest process of activity, which is an average of 92.3%. Furthermore, the activities of making individual work plans and confluence get 84.6%, Making Incident Reports and Participating in seminars as much as 76.9%, Making Arrests 61.5%, Securing evidence and being witnesses in the investigation process is 69.2%, Comply in Education at 61.5%, Being a witness in the trial process and participating in a case title get 46.2% and being an Expert Witness is never done or 0%. The most dominant activities performed by the Forestry Ranger of the TNTBR Center are guarding and patrolling. The patrols are very effective and have an impact on preventing the area's disturbance. Meanwhile, guard activities are less than optimal and ineffective in preventing regional disturbances. The location and position of the Guard Post Resort cannot monitor fishers' activities directly because the working area of the TNTBR area is an open-access water area.

VII. Regional Disturbance in Taka Bonerate National Park.

TNTBR regional disturbances are grouped into two forms: destructive fishing and illegal fishing. The use of explosives or fish bombs, cyanide or anaesthetizing fish, compressor tools to catch fish, or lifting other fish resources are destructive fishing. While Illegal Fishing is in the form of Purse seine or Gae use, taking protected biota, zoning violations, and other licensing violations). Based on the findings of secondary data obtained during data collection, the data on disturbances that occurred in the Taka Bonerate National Park from 2017 to 2020 there were 118 cases or disturbances. The disturbance to the area was destructive fishing as many as 69 incidents and 49 incidents of illegal fishing.

Figure 3.graph of Total Incident Reports Based On Section Of National Park Management Area 1

The data above concluded that regional disturbances in the Taka Bonerate National Park from 2017 to 2020 fluctuated but experienced a declining trend. Based on the working area of the Regional National Park Management Section, the regional disturbance in the Jinato Region II National Park Management Section is higher than one in the Tarupa Region I National Park Management Section Area.

Figure4. graph of total DF and IF disorders based on regional SPTN

Based on the disturbance data above, it can be concluded that the level of disturbance in the form of destructive fishing occurs more in the Working Area of the Management Section of Region II Jinato, while the level of disturbance of cases or incidents of illegal fishing occurs more in the working area of the Management Section of Region I of Tarupa. From 2017 to 2020, regional disturbances in the Taka Bonerate National Park have experienced a decrease in regional disturbances.

VIII. Description and Analysis of Aspects of Forestry Ranger Performance

Based on field observations, 16 Forestry Ranger personnel from the Taka Bonerate National Park Office served in the field, both at the National Park Management Section office and at the Regional Resort office, while a Forestry Ranger Coordinator was at the Central Office.

Table2. TNTBR Forest Ranger Deployment.

No.	Location and Work Area	Total (Personnel)
1.	Central Office	1
2.	Regional I Management Section Office of Tarupa	2
3.	Management Section Office SPTN Region II Jinato	1
4.	Tarupa Resort	3
5.	Tinabo Resort	1
6.	Rajuni Besar Resort	1
7.	Rajuni Resort	2
8.	Jinato Resort	2
8.	Pasitallu Tambuna Resort	3
9.	Pasitallu Tengah Resort	1

Source: TNTBR Office, 2020

Compared with the area and level of disturbance of the area, the Taka Bonerate National Park Center still lacks human resources for the Forestry Ranger. 16 personnel on duty with limited access and facilities deserve extra attention. The Forestry Ranger of the TNTBR Center is the front guard or spearhead to maintain the conservation area's integrity and the natural resources within it. The logical consequence of this number is that area protection activities, especially patrols, require cooperation between resort personnel to meet the person in the team. With limited personnel, the impact on patrol activities is less effective because vulnerable locations cannot be monitored intensively [8].

The Taka Bonerate National Park Center currently has 17 Forestry Ranger personnel, while the requirements or formations of the Forestry Ranger required at the Taka Bonerate National Park Office according to the formation applicable to the Ministry of Environment and Forestry are as follows:

Table3.Forestry Ranger Formation within the Ministry of Forestry

No.	Organizational Unit	Expert Forestry Ranger	Skilled Forestry Ranger
1.	Directorates related to the Forestry Ranger	Min18 Max16	-
2.	The Center for Forestry Ranger	Min28 Max40	Min84 Max123
3.	Central Office related to the Forestry Ranger	Min16 Max22	Min44 Max63
4.	province	Min12 Max48	Min28 Max132
5	Regency/City	Min12 Max60	Min28 Max160

Source:Permenpan RB Number 17 of 2011

Based on the Table 3, the Taka Bonerate National Park Center is categorized as the third one, Central Office related to the Forestry Ranger where there are at least 16 expert forest Ranger officers while currently there are only 4. Refer to the PNS Assessment indicator Based on PP 30 of 2019 concerning Civil Servant Performance Appraisers and the Performance Assessment Indicators of the Forestry Ranger based on the Regulation of the Minister for Administrative Reform of the State Civil Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform, the performance of the Forestry Ranger of the Taka Bonerate National Park Office shows that as many as 17 Forestry Ranger of the Taka Bonerate National Park Office in 2020 **performed well** with an average score of **84.86** and met more than the standard for obtaining the planned and predetermined credit score.

Meanwhile, with the decrease in regional disturbances from 2017 to 2020, it can be concluded that the reduction in regional disturbances cannot be separated from the performance of the forest Ranger in carrying out protection and security duties in the field that have been achieved.

According to Hadari Nawawi [6], performance is achieved, the achievements shown, and the ability to work. Performance is rated as high if a work target can be completed at the right time or does not exceed the time limit provided. Performance becomes low if completed beyond the allotted time limit or not completed at all.

IX. Description and Analysis of Aspects of the Forestry Ranger Strategy

In the 2014-2023 National Park Long-Term Management Plan, the Taka Bonerate National Park Office has a vision, namely "Realizing Taka Bonerate National Park as a People's Area, so that the Taka Bonerate National Park Office still lacks 12 expert level forest Ranger officers to fulfill the minimum formation. Meanwhile, the National Park Office currently has 13 skilled Forestry Ranger for a minimum of 44 people, so that the Taka Bonerate National Park Office is still lacking 29 skilled Forestry Ranger officers to fulfill the minimum formation of the position of front coral reef conservationist, development area and Main Marine Tourism Destinations in Sulawesi". Referring to the second mission, Strengthening and Increasing the Protection of Marine Protected Areas and Law Enforcement, the objectives are:

- 1) Increased protection of water conservation areas, living natural resources, and ecosystems contained therein.
- 2) Increased law enforcement efforts in the TNTBR area.

- 3) The more stable the participation of the community and other parties in protecting and enforcing the law in TNTBR.
- 4) Increasing the role of the community and stakeholders in KSDAHE management partnerships; for this reason, the Taka Bonerate National Park Center in maintaining the integrity of the conservation area focuses on protecting and securing the area by prioritizing the tasks of the forest Ranger and improving the performance of the Forestry Ranger as listed in the second mission as part of the strategic steps that need to be carried out properly.

According to Maulana Agus in the Manajemen Strategik book, the first step in the strategic management process is the determination of the Organization's Vision and Mission. The vision and mission of the organization will be the general guidelines for all organizational activities. Departing from the vision and mission, the organization prepares plans and activities to realize its vision and mission. In the decision-making hierarchy, the vision and mission are strategic decisions [7].

As an elaboration and implementation of the Vision and Mission of Taka Bonerate National Park, the protection and security of the Taka Bonerate National Park area are carried out by the Forestry Ranger with strategic steps (Source of RPJP Taka Bonerate National Park Office) including:

1. Community involvement in Area Protection and Security activities through Community Forestry Ranger Partners
2. Involvement of other law enforcement officers in the protection and security of the area
3. Increase the intensity of security patrol activities
4. Increasing the number of Forestry Ranger Personnel in Area Protection and Security.

This strategy is subjectively chosen. However, it has also considered various factors and identified strategic options based on objective information involving the parties. At the organizational level of the Taka Bonerate National Park Office, this work plan has been prepared by involving all elements of staff in the office and the field.

According to Maulana Agus in the Manajemen Strategik book, "Strategic analysis and selection basically involves subjective decision-making based on objective information" [7].

In this study, which is supported by data obtained from informants, namely 17 Forestry Ranger and 4 Structural Officials and 8 Community/Working Partners, the choice of strategies for the Protection and Security of the Taka Bonerate National Park Area is as follows:

Table 4. Alternative Options for TNTBR Protection and Security strategies

No.	Alternative Strategy	Total
1.	Engage with Community	7
2.	Involvement of Related Apparatus	5
3.	Increasing Intensity of Patrol Activities	11
4.	Increasing Number of Personnel	6

Source: The author, 2021

Out of those alternative strategies for securing the TNTBR area, most respondents chose to increase the intensity of Patrol activities.

Figure 5. optimal protection and security activities in reducing interference

We can see in Fig.5 that increasing patrols' intensity will prevent regional disturbances. This is in line with the opinion of several communities and partners from the Forestry Service Office of the Taka Bonerate National Park that increasing the intensity of patrols is considered capable of preventing regional disturbances in the Taka Bonerate National Park.

From several strategies carried out by the Forestry Ranger in protecting and securing the area, including involving the community, involving the relevant authorities, increasing the intensity of patrols, and increasing the number of personnel, the most effective way is to increase the intensity of patrols.

This research is in line with Medi Haeirullah research entitled *Efektifitas Kinerja Polisi Kehutanan Dalam Penanganan Gangguan Kawasan di Taman Nasional Gunung Gede Pangrango* (The Effectiveness of Forestry Ranger Performance in Handling Regional Disturbances in Gunung Gede Pangrango National Park). The objectives of this research are: (1) to identify the factors that influence the effectiveness of the forest Ranger performance in handling regional disturbances; 2) Measuring the effectiveness of Forestry Ranger performance in handling regional disturbances, and 3) Formulate a strategy to improve the performance of the forest and forest Ranger. This research was conducted using a descriptive analysis method with a quantitative approach and SWOT analysis. Forestry Ranger data was collected by census on 39 forest Ranger at the Gede Pangrango National Park Center (BBTNGGP) by filling out a questionnaire and structured interviews conducted in January-March 2017. Improving the performance of the Forestry Ranger is to increase patrols and approach the community [9].

X. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion, the results of this study can be concluded as follows:

- a. The Taka Bonerate National Park Forestry Ranger dominate the protection and security of the area by Patrol and Guard. Patrols are very effective and have an impact in preventing regional disturbances, while guarding activities are less effective because the location of the guard post resort with fishing activities is difficult to monitor because the working area is an open-access waters area. Regional disturbances in Taka Bonerate National Park are divided into two kinds: destructive fishing and illegal fishing, which from 2017 to 2020 fluctuated but tended to decline. The level of disturbance in the National Park Management section of Jinato region II is higher than the National Park Management Section of Tarupa region I.
- b. The performance of the Forestry Ranger of the Taka Bonerate National Park Office based on the average value of the achievement of the Employee Performance Target in 2020 is in the good category with the highest score of 84.86 (scores 76 – 90 good category), this is in line with the decreasing trend of regional disturbances. In addition, referring to Article 3 Permenpan RB Number: 17 of 2011 at the UPT National Park Center Taka Bonerate, there is still a shortage of 12 expert forest Ranger officers and 29

skilled forest Ranger officers.

Referring to the Second Mission of the National Park Management Plan to strengthen and improve the Protection of Marine Protected Areas and Law Enforcement, the Protection and Security Strategies carried out by the National Park Authority Forestry Ranger are: (1) Involving the community in the protection and security of Forestry Ranger Partner Community activities (2) Involving Related Law Enforcement Officials (3) Increasing Patrol Intensity (4) Proposing Additional Personnel. According to the respondent, of the four strategies, the most effective is Reducing the Intensity of Patrol Activities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Yudhawati, I, *Analisis Pengaruh Motivasi dan Integritas terhadap Kinerja Polisi Kehutanan di Departemen Kehutanan*, magister diss., IPB University, Bogor, 2007.
- [2] Simamora, Hendry, *Manajemen sumber daya manusia* (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2006).
- [3] Amiruddin, *Pengantar Metode Penelitian Hukum* (Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 2012).
- [4] Jakarta Suardi, *Analisis Pelaksanaan Tugas Operasional Polda Sultra Dalam Upaya Pembinaan Keamanan Dan Ketertiban Masyarakat*. magister diss., Universitas Terbuka, 2010.
- [5] Sultan S., *Strategi Penanggulangan Gangguan Hutan di Kabupaten Sinjai*. magister diss., Hasanuddin University, 2018.
- [6] N. Hadari, *Evaluasi dan manajemen kinerja di lingkungan perusahaan dan industri*. (Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press, 2006).
- [7] Agus. M, *Manajemen strategik*, (Tangerang Selatan:Alpha Aksara, 2015).
- [8] TNTBR Office, *Rencana Pengelolaan Taman Nasional Taka Bonerate 2014-2023*. Selayar (ID), 2014
- [9] Haerullah, M., Faktor Internal yang Memengaruhi Efektivitas Kinerja Polisi Kehutanan dalam Penanganan Gangguan Kawasan di Taman Nasional Gunung Gede Pangrango, *Journal of Natural Resources and Environmental Management*, 8(3), 2018, 347-354.